

dissociation of the complex $M(RH)_2$. It has been followed in case of $Cu(RH)_2$ and the pk_2 and pk_1 values are found to be 5.80, 8.24 and 6.05, 8.43, respectively for $Cu(R^pH)_2$ and $Cu(R^bH)_2$. Possibilities of the formation of polynuclear species have been checked using two different concentrations (0.005 and 0.0075 M) of metal ions with the same concentration (0.02 M) of RH_2^+ .

The overall stability of the complexes has been found to follow Irving-Williams order, *i.e.* $Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II}$. The stability order of the complexes in the ligand order is $R^pH_2^+ > R^bH_2^+$. The formation of weak complexes by $R^bH_2^+$ than $R^pH_2^+$ is probably due to steric effect⁹. The protonation and complex formation may be depicted as in Scheme 1.

References

1. N. N. GHOSH and M. M. NANDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 274, 331.
2. M. M. NANDI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1977, 46, 698.
3. M. M. NANDI and A. K. MISHRA, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1981, 44, 19.
4. N. N. GHOSH and M. M. NANDI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 778.
5. N. N. GHOSH and M. M. NANDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 643; 1977, 54, 139; 1978, 55, 749.
6. M. M. NANDI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, 15, 809.
7. M. M. NANDI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 493.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry" E.L.B.S., London, 1978, p. 177.
9. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
10. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
11. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI and H. ROSSOTTI, "The Determination of Stability Constants", McGraw-Hill, London, 1961, p. 88.

Near-infrared Spectroscopic Study of Aquo-organic Mixtures

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MANY of the interesting behaviours of water are due to hydrogen bonding, which plays a very important role in the interaction energy¹. Different theories, both continuum and mixed models, have been proposed but general agreement is still lacking². Many different studies have been made on the effect of solutes, generally of electrolytes, on water structure³⁻⁸. However, studies with non-electrolytes, like sugar⁴, alcohol⁹ and acetone¹⁰ *etc.* seem to be rather scanty. The relative accessibility of near-infrared region measurements make the

study in this region easy and useful for analytical purposes as well as for molecular structural studies. Literature survey seems to indicate that no study has so far been done on the effect of alcohols and acetone on water structure by the use of near-infrared region. Hence, an attempt has been made in this note to report on the observations made on the water-methanol and water-acetone mixtures in 0-100% concentration region by near-infrared spectra (0.8-1.1 μ).

The spectra of pure water, methanol and acetone over this very near-infrared region are interesting. For water, there is only one maximum at 0.99 μ , while methanol and acetone show two maxima, one on either side of the 0.99 μ band of water. The absorptivity of methanol was much lower than that of water and the absorption by acetone was almost negligible in this wavelength range. Air was used as reference in all cases. The absorbance of pure water at maximum is 0.182 (0.99 μ), and that of pure methanol 0.053 (1.03 μ) and 0.013 (0.927 μ). The spectra of water-methanol mixtures are shown in Fig. 1. It is found that as the concentration of water increases in the mixture, the 1.03 μ band of methanol gets blue-shifted and the shift continues till it coincides with 0.99 μ band of pure water. Water-methanol mixtures show isosbestic points at 1.045 and 0.935 μ at 30°. This indicates some sort of interaction between the components.

Fig. 1. Near infrared spectra of water-methanol mixture (v/v) at 30°: Water (1) 100, (2) 80, (3) 60, (4) 40, (5) 20, (6) 10, and (7) 0%.

The spectra of water-acetone mixtures are appreciably different (Fig. 2) from that of the water-methanol. It has been reported in the literature¹¹ that acetone shows strong absorption around 1.0 μ . However, the present study does not indicate the same though at 1.125 μ absorption begins to increase and a maximum with a shoulder is observed at 1.190 μ . The presence of 0.9 μ band with little change in absorptivity from that of pure acetone is noted in the spectra of water-acetone mixtures over all the concentration ranges. It is evident that a perceptible blue-shift with respect to the pure acetone absorption band at 1.02 μ occurs as soon as water is added to the acetone, like that in water-

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methanol system. But unlike the latter system, no further blue-shift occurs when the concentration of water is more than 50%, and no isosbestic points are observed.

Fig. 2. Near infrared spectra of water-acetone mixtures (v/v) at 30°: Water (1) 100, (2) 80, (3), 60, (4) 40, (5) 20, (6) 10, and (7) 0%.

It has been postulated earlier¹⁰ that an association compound between water and acetone is probably present in water-acetone mixtures, since at 2.7 μ the absorption coefficient was several times greater than that of water at 3 μ band. But from Fig. 2 such postulation is difficult. It is rather postulated that if such water-acetone association compound due to interaction between the components, is really present then it is not possible to recognise it by the near-infrared spectra (0.8-1.1 μ), though as mentioned earlier the presence of two isosbestic points in water-methanol systems indicate the interaction between these two components.

Experimental

A Shimadzu 500 spectrophotometer with temperature control was used. Empty quartz cell was used as reference. Path length was 1 cm. Water was triple-distilled. Methanol and acetone were passed through fused CaCl₂ columns and then distilled. Mixtures were made by volume proportions.

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References

1. W. A. P. LUCK in "The Hydrogen Bond", eds. P. SCHUSTER, G. ZUNDEL and C. SANDORFY, North Holland Publishing Co., Amsterdam, 1976, Vol. III, p. 1369.

2. W. A. P. LUCK in "Structure of Water and Aqueous Solutions", ed. W. A. P. LUCK, Verlag Chemie, Weinheim, 1974.
3. R. SUHRMANN and F. BREYER, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1931, 19, 772.
4. E. GANZ *Z. Phys. Chem. B*, 1936, 33, 163.
5. E. GANZ, *Z. Phys. Chem. B*, 1937, 35, 1.
6. R. SUHRMANN and F. BREYER, *Z. Phys. Chem. B*, 1933, 23, 193.
7. H. YAMATERA, B. FITZPATRICK and G. GORDON, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1964, 14, 268.
8. R. E. VERRALL in "Water—A Comprehensive Treatise", ed. F. FRANKS, Plenum Press, New York, Vol. 3, p. 211.
9. D. WILLIAMS, R. D. WEATHERFORD and E. K. PLYLER, *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, 1936, 26, 149.
10. D. WILLIAMS and E. K. PLYLER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, 4, 154.
11. G. B. M. SUTHERLAND, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, 9, 274.
12. R. M. BADGER and S. H. BAUER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 839.

C.E.C. of Roots of Gram (*Cicer arietinum*) Crop and its Relation to Age and Nutrient Content of Plant

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C. E.C. of roots has an important role in plant nutrition because plants take in their nutrients through roots and if the exchange capacity of roots is high, plants may take more nutrients from the soil. The C.E.C. of the plant roots is highly affected by age of the plant¹⁻⁵. Nutrient concentration of plant at different physiological stages of growth is influenced by the root C.E.C. which has also been expressed by many workers^{2,6,7}. So the present investigation has an important value to study the effect of root C.E.C. on phosphorus, iron and manganese content of different varieties of gram crop at their different physiological growth stages.

Experimental

The experiment was carried out in a net house. Two varieties of gram crop, namely BG-39/2 and BG-231 were sown in fertile alluvial soil (pH, O.C., total N, C : N ratio, C.E.C., available P and total Mn were 6.5, 0.48%, 0.08%, 5.51, 16.90 meq/100 g soil, 2.00 ppm and 33.0 ppm, respectively) taken in a pot without any further addition of nutrients. Plant roots and plant samples were taken at 3 stages, i.e. 30, 45 and 60 days after sowing. The roots were washed in distilled water. After drying, they were milled to pass through 20-mesh sieve and analysed for their C.E.C. by adopting the method of Crooke⁸. It has been reported^{1,9} that keeping